

EHT = 15.01 kV
WD = 17.0 mm

Signal A = SE1
Mag = 50 X

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AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE RATE DEPENDENT BEHAVIOUR OF THROUGH- THICKNESS REINFORCEMENT IN Z-PINNED CFRP LAMINATES

Huifang Liu

Specimen

- Z-pin
 - Method: Direct Insertion (DI)
 - Material: BMI/T300
 - Diameter: 0.28mm
- Laminate
 - Thickness: 4.6mm//PTFE//4.6mm
 - Pin matrix: 3*3, 2% areal density

Experiment

- Incident Bar: Titanium bar, $D = 10\text{mm}$
- Transmission Bar: Aluminum tube, $\text{OD} = 6\text{mm}$, $\text{ID} = 4\text{mm}$

Experiment

- High-speed camera: Kirana
- Displacement: DIC
- Force: Strain gauge on the bar

Overall results

Pull-out failure

Z-pin breakage

Loading rate effect

1. Resin failure
2. Interface between Z-pin and laminate
3. Debonding between fibre and BMI resin in Z-pin
4. Fibre breakage in Z-pin

Loading rate effect

QS

- Debonding between BMI resin and T300 fibre in Z-pin

Loading rate effect

HR

- Fibre splitting then break in Z-pin
- Debonding between BMI resin and T300 fibre in Z-pin

In situ temperature effect

Cold

- Pure tension

In situ temperature effect

- In situ temperature effect

In situ temperature effect

45

60

75

RT

In situ temperature effect

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Hot

Cold

- In situ temperature effect

Conclusions

- The loading rate mainly affect the pull-out of behaviour of Z-pin;
- In-situ temperature condition has a significant influence on the mechanical behaviour of Z-pin:
 - Room temperature gives the best performance for all the loading conditions, while the cold condition gives the worst response;
 - Hot temperature stays in the middle, but the pull-out behaviour is quite unstable especially when β equals to 15;
 - Under cold condition, the Z-pin tends to break even when the load is tension dominated.

Thanks

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